

Index of Supplemental Materials, Data, Code, and Research Materials

For Whaley et al. (2022) "Standards-Compliant General Protocol for a Systematic Review" as submitted to *Evidence-Based Toxicology*

Item	Link
Document templates for complex protocol data that cannot be directly entered into the general-purpose protocol	https://osf.io/h7w68/
List of labels for the protocol data	https://osf.io/vw4e3
Labelled template for generating automated protocol documentation	https://osf.io/nckwu
Draft protocol from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/zr78y
JSON database from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/63tmz
PDF of data entered into Protocols.io on test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/t3z98
Full set of documents created for test run and uploaded to OSF as per general-purpose protocol instructions (test run #7)	https://osf.io/m35px/
Code for JSON conversion from Protocols.io protocol run and document generation	https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD